

Applying keyword extraction combined with word embedding in the analysis of originality in research papers

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Abstract

In this paper, we extend the work of Shibayama et al. (2021) on the estimation of the disruption index (D) of a focal paper, by changing the text to be analyzed when assessing the semantic distance between two references. Instead of using only the words of the whole text of titles and abstracts, we implement a preliminary stage where the most relevant words and phrases in the titles and abstracts are identified through a machine learning algorithm. That avoids the contamination of the word embedding procedure with common words that do not reflect the scientific content of the references and may contribute to biased results in the disruption indexes. We applied this procedure to the Physical Review Letters (PRL) Milestone papers, following the work of Bornmann and Tekles (2021), to test its validity. For the PRL Milestone papers database, the originality scores generated with the proposed method are higher than those generated with the approach by Shibayama et al. (2021).

Introduction

Although the abundance of scientific production has boomed in recent decades, the originality and disruptiveness of published papers is still a controversial topic. On the one hand, it is difficult to believe that in all these works there are different and relevant ideas from those already published and, on the other hand, the criteria for measuring originality are not so easy to identify and apply, even more, when it comes to a large-scale assessment. Disruptive papers are discrepant from others by launching new tracks to solve the most relevant questions in their fields. In recent years, automated metrics for measuring the paper's originality or disruptiveness in science have been proposed and studied (Bornmann & Tekles, 2021). These indicators were designed to be applied without the need to have a field expert analyze the scientific papers and identify the new ideas they present.

Some recent studies proposed a way to estimate the disruption index (D) of a focal paper (FP) (Shibayama & Wang, 2019; Wu et al., 2019). Three variables participate in the calculation of D : the number of articles that cited the FP but didn't cite its references (n_i), the number of articles that cited both the FP and its references (n_j), and the number of articles just cited its references (n_k). D is calculated by the difference between the proportion of n_i and n_j . That is, if the FP is cited together with its references, then it tends to represent the same concepts as the previous ones, not being something new that deserves to be highlighted. Applying D , Wu et al. (2019) analyzed more than 65 million papers, patents, and software products (1954–2014), revealing that disruption in science is more likely to happen in small research groups than in large ones which are more dedicated on consolidating the models already proposed (Wu et al., 2019; Azoulay, 2019). Other studies have proposed variations of this indicator, in which n_j depends on whether the FP references have also been cited by other articles from the same journal or year as the FP (Bu et al., 2021; Bornmann et al., 2020a; Bornmann et al., 2020b). In this improved model, the fact that some of the FP references are "highly cited papers", and, therefore with a high probability of being cited does not reduce the originality of the FP.

To understand the performance of these indicators to estimate the paper's originality, Bornmann and Tekles (2021) analyzed their results against an experts-based list. The authors used the Physical Review Letter (PRL) Milestones (<https://journals.aps.org/prl/50years/milestones>) since this paper list is recognized by field experts as composed of disruptive research papers. Bornmann and Tekles showed that indicators that consider how strong the citation links between citing papers and cited references are perform better. However, the measures of originality and disruptiveness are uncertain and field-dependent, making the subject challenging. In this case, the use of citation counts is a serious limitation since there are major criticisms against the use of this parameter as a bibliometric indicator. Another interesting question to investigate is related to papers that present original ideas to solve a problem that has been extensively researched in the area, and that, therefore, may present a low D for citing many works that others will later cite as well. To estimate the paper's relative originality, Shibayama et al. (2021) proposed an approach based on word embedding. Word embedding is a popular technique in recent machine learning to represent words by multi-dimension vectors (Hain et al., 2021). The authors used the title and abstract content of the FP references in the biomedicine field. They assigned a word embedding to these contents and calculated the vector distance between every pair of references of a FP. In this way, the greater the distance of the vectors, the greater the degree of originality of the FP. One of the ways they used to validate the model was by comparing its results with a self-reported novelty score collected from a questionnaire survey. One problem with this approach is that applying word embedding to all the text generates an average indicator for each paper that might be contaminated by common English words used in science. Therefore, those generated vectors may not reflect the scientific content of the paper. The aim of this study is to address this issue by combining the work of Shibayama et al. (2021) and Campos et al. (2020). In this new approach, instead of using the entire text of the title and abstract of the references, we only use their most relevant words, identified through the Machine Learning algorithm YAKE! (Campos et al., 2020). To test the validity of the method, we applied both our method and the one from Shibayama et al. (2021) to the Physical Review Letter (PRL) Milestones database and we compared the originality results generated from both methods.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. We present in the next section the methodological approach proposed, and in the following section, the preliminary results. Finally, in the last section, we present the main conclusions and future research steps.

Data and methods

The following sections describe each of the steps of the model used in this study, which is represented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Step-by-step of the model

Word embedding model

To train the data and build the word embedding model using specific semantics, we retrieved data from the titles and abstracts of 1,715,000 Scopus Physics field papers published in 1990-2023. As a criterium for this research in progress, we used all articles published in 1990-2023 from the 35 higher Journal Citation Reports (Clarivate) journals. As an extension of this project, we plan to include all other Clarivate journals and the remaining periods. This set contains over 1,500,000 different tokens (single words and bigrams). The goal is to configure the model to better represent the semantics of the words in Physics. Word embedding train is an iterative process of word-similarity evaluation in which the predictions are faced against the known relationship between the words. In this process, it is crucial to train our own word embeddings using our training data so that the research field concepts of the training corpus can be better represented. We used the Word2Vec (Bojanowski et al., 2017; Church, 2017), a library for efficient learning of word representations and sentence classification that is able to define the word embedding. For greater consistency between the tokens that will be used in the calculation and the trained word embedding, it is better that the cleaning performed in model training be the same as that performed in the papers that will have their novelty measured.

Originality estimate

Generally, to calculate the vector that represents a text, authors use all the words in the text, and then they determine the vector of each word and make an average of all these vectors. In a previous model, Shibayama et al. (2021) used the same approach in the biomedicine field. However, to compare two texts and find similarities regarding their scientific content, we propose that the most relevant words representing the title or abstract are extracted before calculating the average. In this way, we suppose the average will better represent the concepts, methods, theories, and subjects associated with the text. For that, we use the YAKE! method (Campos et al., 2020), which is already widely used in scientific research. YAKE!, a machine-learning algorithm, automatically identifies the most relevant keywords within the text. Thus, the method used here can be structured in the following items: (i) For each FP we accessed the titles and abstracts of the references; (ii) We extract the most relevant words and phrases (labels) from titles and abstracts using YAKE!; (iii) We define the vectors (v_i) of each label using the pre-trained word embeddings model ("Word embedding model" section); (iv) We average the sets of vectors for each reference (v_i) – each reference will be represented by only one vector;

(v) We calculate the distance of similarity (d_{ij}) for each pair of references i and j in the FP by the cosine similarity, according to Equation (1).

$$d_{ij} = 1 - \frac{v_i \cdot v_j}{|v_i| |v_j|} \quad (1)$$

We repeat the process for all FPs. At the end of the above process, the papers with the highest d_{ij} values are considered to have the highest relative originality.

Comparison of the two methods

We used the PRL milestones (39 papers) as FP, already used for this purpose by Bornmann and Tekles (2021), as a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of the originality score, as described in the previous section. Using the Scopus database, we gathered the titles and abstracts of these papers' cited references (470 papers). Using this data, we calculated the d_{ij} scores using the proposed method (first using only the titles and then using only the abstracts, as in Shibayama et al (2021)) and, for comparison purposes, also using the method by Shibayama et al. (2021).

Preliminary results

As a preliminary result of the word embedding training, we calculated the cosine similarity (c_{ij}) of some words from the context of Physics taken from PhySH, a Physics subject classification scheme developed by the American Physical Society (physh.org). Our preliminary objective, with this small initial dataset, is to parameterize the model through known results. We used the eight areas of Physics as in the research of Pech et al. (2022). Figure 2 presents, on the left, the labels used, and on the right, the calculated c_{ij} for each one of the 780 pairs of labels.

Figure 2. Physics subfields and the labels used to train the word embedding model (on the left) and cosine similarity (c_{ij}) values (from -1 (no similarity, in green) to 1 (completely similar, in red) for labels of the eight Physics subfields (on the right)

Although the word embedding model can still be better adjusted by expanding the articles database, these preliminary results describe reasonably well the similarity of the Physics labels used.

To compare the results between the model proposed by this work and the previous model (Shibayama et al., 2021) we calculated the values of d_{ij} (Equation 1) for each FP (here, the PRL Milestone papers). With these values we obtained, for each FP, the d_{ij} corresponding to the

following percentiles: 100; 99; 95; 90; 80 and 50 (Shibayama et al., 2021). This procedure was performed according to the previous model (d_{ij}) and for the model proposed in this paper (d_{ij_YAKE}), for titles and abstracts.

Figure 3. Distance similarity (d_{ij}) differences.

Fig. 3 shows the result of the difference between these two approaches for each d_{ij} value. There are 234 values (events); i.e., six d_{ij} (one for each of the six percentiles) associated with each of the 39 FPs. The events were placed in ascending order of d_{ij} differences along the x axis. The charts in Fig. 3 show that, in almost all cases, the difference between the originality scores (d_{ij}) is positive, or, in other words, that the originality scores are higher for the proposed model.

A similar result can also be seen through the boxplots presented in Fig. 4 for titles and abstracts generated by both models. In this figure, for each one of the 6 percentiles used in this comparison, we present the boxplot of the originality scores (d_{ij}) generated using either the abstracts or the titles of the references of each milestone paper and using either the proposed method ($_YAKE$) or the Shibayama et al. (2021) method.

Figure 4. Comparison of the boxplots of the originality scores (d_{ij}) - the darker boxes represent the proposed method ($_YAKE$) and the lighter boxes the approach of Shibayama et al. (2021)

Conclusions

This paper represents an improvement on the paper of Shibayama et al. (2021) to estimate the novelty in scientific papers using word embedding. Considering papers recognized with a high level of "disruption" in science, the results obtained better support than the previous ones. Furthermore, the proposed model builds and trains the word embedding tokens, allowing for a more contextualized representation within the field in which it will be used.

As future steps, we will address some of the limitations of this preliminary work by: (i) extending the word embedding training to improve the vector representation of the labels in the Physics field; (ii) the identification (with machine learning procedures) and use of N-grams labels to improve the context of the reference (Le et al., 2019); (iii) further developments in the procedure to calculate the originality scores; (iv) further validation of the model, using large sets of non-milestones papers in the field; and (v) comparison analysis of the proposed originality index with others.

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